

ISic3389

I.Sicily inscription 3389

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary (?)

Material

limestone

Object

architrave

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Megara Hyblaea

Place of origin (modern)

Megara Iblea

Provenance

necropolis excavations 1891

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Museo Archeologico
Regionale Paolo Orsi, inventory 10869

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI330080

1. [— — —]τόι Κυβοῖ [τις]

2.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645660

PHI 330080

Bibliography

1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum*

graecum. At 26.1089

undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined 1876-.

Notizie degli scavi di antichità. *Notizie degli scavi di antichità*. At 198-199 fig.6

Guarducci, M. 1967-1978. Epigrafia greca. Rome. At vol.1 316 no.7 fig.154

Manni Piraino, M.T. 1975. Koiné alfabetica fra Siracusa, Megara Iblea e

Selinunte?. *Kokalos*. 21: 121-153. At 146-147 no.10 fig.32.1

Gallavotti, C. 1975-1976. Scritture arcaiche della Sicilia e di Rodi. *Helikon*. 15-16:

71-117. At 111-113

Arena, R. 1996. Iscrizioni Greche Archaiche di Sicilia e Magna Grecia. Iscrizioni

di Sicilia. I. Iscrizioni di Megara Iblea e Selinunte. Pisa. At no.11 tav.5.1

Licensed under a Creative

Commons-Attribution 4.0 licence.

Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-23): ISic3389. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4388489>